

DESIGN OF BATTERY SYSTEM FOR SOLAR POWERED STREET LIGHT

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Abstract:

This paper proposes energy efficient of automatic street lighting system based on PIR motion sensor. The main objective is to design energy efficient Smart Street light for energy conservation in existing streetlight. While, the controlling and managing of the system is based on the movement of vehicles and. The system was programmed to automatically turn off during the hours of daylight and only operate during the time when vehicles cross the motion sensor. The system consists of solar panel, battery, PIR sensor, LED light. Many times we see that street lights are remain switched ON even during when no vehicles cross the light, this is lot of wastes of electricity while India is facing lack of electricity. Another thing is that these traditional street lamps e.g. Sodium vapors, Metal halide, Incandescent, Fluorescent lamps consumes more power for a specified Lumen per Watt as compared with new advanced Led Lights. Streetlights can be operated free of cost by using automatic controlled, self-powered, efficient solar LED street light.

Key Words: Smart LED Street Light, Solar, Energy Efficient, Street Lighting, PIR Sensor & Battery Management System

1. Introduction:

In entire world there are more than 300 million of street lights, which emits 100 million tons of carbon dioxide per year. 40% of energy is wasted which costs around 20 billion dollars. Therefore for economical operation of street lights and reduction of carbon footprints, High efficient LED luminaire with smart control of illumination level is the demand and need of time. About India, India consumes 18% of electricity for street lighting and residential lighting in which street lighting takes major part, while India is facing shortage of electricity. If all existing streetlight replaced with LED lights then India will be benefited by 5,500 cores of rupees every year and reduction in CO₂ emission. Therefore, this paper highlights the energy efficient street lighting design using LED lamps through intelligent sensor interface for controlling intensity of light. Still today almost all street lights are switched manually and thus due to manual error they are not switched at proper time, sometimes streetlights are remains ON during daytime. The above problems of switching can be avoided using motion sensor allows controlling light intensity which ensures energy saving and economical.

2. Objective of the Proposed System:

The proposed smart solar LED streetlight can be operated free of cost with sufficient solar charging. The battery starts charging in daytime via PV solar panel. The movement of vehicles can be detected by using motion sensor. With this automation technique, capacity (Ah) of battery required is much less a compared to conventional solar LED street light. This is beneficial by many aspects like economic, environmental, lighting performance, reduction in road accidents, thief and crime.

3. Methodology:

Two main parts have been discussed under this topic. The hardware specification of each component is given below. Flow chart is also explained here.

A. Hardware Specification:

- Solar Panel: As the name implies, these are cells that are grown from a single crystal. The monocrystalline solar PV panel is more efficient than polycrystalline panel. Efficiency is about 18%. High Efficient Monocrystalline solar panel generates electricity during day time and it is stored in battery.
- Battery: It is a type of rechargeable battery, which uses lithium ion Phosphate as a cathode material. Li ion Ph batteries have somewhat high energy density, light weight offer longer lifetime. Inherently safer hence lithium ion Phosphate is popular among all storage batteries.
- PIR (Passive Infrared Sensor) Motion Sensor: An infrared sensor [6] is an electronic device that emits in order to sense some aspects of the surroundings. An IR sensor can measure the heat of an object as well as detects the motion. These types of sensors measures only infrared radiation, rather than emitting it, that is called as a passive IR sensor. Usually in the infrared spectrum, all the objects radiate some form of thermal radiations. These types of radiations are invisible to our eyes that can be detected by an infrared sensor.

- LED (Light Emitting Diode): With the technological advancement in semiconductor material, a LED lamp produces light within visible range spectrum, therefore it has highest efficiency than incandescent, sodium vapour and other lamps. Therefore LED lamps world widely accepted for many lighting applications along with for Street lighting purpose. LED lamps having highest lifespan from 50,000Hrs to 1,00,000 Hrs and efficiency of 100 to 120 lm/w.

B. Flowchart:

Figure 1: Flowchart of the proposed system

4. Block Diagram of Proposed System:

Figure 2: Block diagram of Smart Street LED light with PIR sensor

During day time solar panel produces electricity and it stored in the battery. If any person or vehicle passes nearby streetlight, motion sensor activates and gives command to increase brightness to 100%. After preset time and if there is no movement detected, hence the street light turns OFF. Normally streetlight will operate from electricity stored in the battery. If battery is not charged sufficiently due to cloudy weather condition then streetlight will automatically switch to utility supply.

5. Hardware Implementation:

Figure 3: Prototype model

Figure 4: Prototype Model

The proposed system is useful to save electricity when there is no vehicles passes by and provides automatic on and off.

6. Comparative Output:

The streetlight with solar PV panel does not consumes any power from utility supply, therefore operates free of cost within provided backup from battery

Figure 5: Power Consumption of different Streetlight systems

7. Conclusion:

In this paper, the smart solar LED streetlight is presented. As a conclusion, around 70% to 85% of power consumption can be reduced by using this system as compared with existing sodium vapour streetlights. This is best solution to current street lighting system. Furthermore, the streetlight can be operated with free of cost providing efficient solar panel and battery. The smart solar LED streetlight system provides better illumination, optimum usage of electricity with reducing operational and maintenance cost after installation

compare to high pressure sodium lamp and others. Number of street lights can be controlled providing communication between them using wireless sensor. The streetlight can also be energized with footstep generation system. Facilities such as mobile charging point and Wi-Fi spot can be provided to areas near IT parks, malls and different institutes. The proposed streetlight can be integrated with CCTV camera, water level monitoring, and air quality monitoring systems. The above various parameters can be monitored and people of city, nearby area can be alerted for any emergency condition.

8. References:

1. Long, X.; Liao, R, Zhou, J, "Development of street lighting system-based novel high-brightness LED modules," *Optoelectronics, IET*, vol.3, no.1, pp.40-46, February 2009 doi: 10.1049/ietopt: 20070076.
2. Xingming Long; Jing Zhou, "An intelligent driver for Light Emitting Diode Street Lighting," *Automation Congress, 2008. WAC 2008, World*, vol., no., pp.1-5, Sept. 28 2008-Oct. 2 2008
3. Po-Yen Chen; Yi-Hua Liu; Yeu-Torng Yau; Hung-Chun Lee; , "Development of an energy efficient street light driving system," *Sustainable Energy Technologies, 2008. ICSET 2008, IEEE International Conference on* vol., no., pp.761-764, 24-27 Nov. 2008 doi:10.1109/ICSET.2008.4747108.
4. Alzubaidi, S.; Soori, P.K., "Study on energy efficient street lighting system design," *Power Engineering and Optimization Conference (PEDCO) Melaka, Malaysia, 2012 IEEE International*, vol., no., pp. 291, 295, 6-7 June 2012, doi: 10.1109/PEOCO.2012.62308
5. Ansis Avotins, Peteris Apse-Apsitis, Maris Kunickis, Leonids Ribickis, "Towards smart street LED lighting systems and preliminary energy saving results", *Power and Electrical Engineering of Riga Technical University (RTUCON) 2014 55th International Scientific Conference on*, pp. 130-135, 2014.
6. Bruno A., Di Franco F., Rascona G. 2012. Smart street lighting. *EE Times* <http://www.eetimes.com/design/smart-energydesign/4375167/Smart-street-lighting>
7. Abdelmoughni Toubal, Billel Bengherbia, Mohamed Ouldzmirli, Mohamed Maazouz, "Energy efficient street lighting control system using wireless sensor networks", *Modelling Identification and Control (ICMIC) 2016 8th International Conference on*, pp. 919-924, 2016
8. *Electronics for You*, Volume 2014 August, <http://www.efymag.com>
9. Balasubramanian Indu Rani, Ganesan Saravana Ilango, Chilakapati Nagamani 'Control Strategy for Power Flow Management in a PV System Supplying DC Loads' *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, Vol. 60, No. 8, August 2013.
10. Senjyu, T., Nakaji, T., Uezato, K., and Funabashi, T. A Hybrid Power System Using Alternative Energy Facilities in Isolated Island. *IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion*, vol. 20, no. 2, June, 2005.
11. S. Armstrong, M. E. Glavin and W. G. Hurley, "Comparison of battery charging algorithms for standalone photovoltaic systems," 2008 IEEE power Electronics Specialists Conference, pp. 1469 – 1475, June 2008
12. D. Bica, D. Cristian, "Photovoltaic laboratory for study of renewable solar energy," 43rd International Universities Power Engineering Conference, pp. 1 – 5, Sep 2008.
13. Cody Hill, Dongmei Chen Member, "Development of a Real-Time Testing Environment for Battery Energy Storage Systems in Renewable Energy Applications".